

Artificial intelligence and teaching practice: Pre-service teachers' perceptions in Greece

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Abstract

The objectives of the study, which was conducted in 2025, were both to explore 344 pre-service teachers' perceptions and attitudes on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ways of implementing it in their Teaching Practice, based on the TPACK model, and examine the differences regarding gender and age, through a questionnaire which was designed based on the tool developed by Chounta et al. (2022). According to the results, pre-service teachers at the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) seem to be familiar with the concept and have used relevant applications. However, the use and the aim of using it during their Teaching Practice seems to be limited. The results highlight the necessity for preparing future teachers to address educational challenges through the utilization of AI tools.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Teaching Practice; Primary Education; Pre-Service Teachers; Perceptions.*

JEL Classification: I21; I23; O33.

1. Definitions and functions of artificial intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the most dynamic and transformative fields of modern science and technology. The term refers to the ability of computing systems to perform tasks that, until recently, required human intelligence (e.g., reasoning, problem solving, decision-making) and use the data they collect and store to improve themselves (Russell & Norvig, 2021; Yau et al., 2022). In this way, the machines become capable of 'understanding' the environment around them and, by receiving ready-made data (input data) or data via sensors (e.g., AI cameras, distance sensors, etc.), to parameterize their responses based on them (European Commission, 2022).

The basic functions of AI as realized in different scientific disciplines and technological applications have developed in a multidimensional, interrelated way. Such functions are: a) AI handles large amounts of data, finds patterns and draws important inferences with increasingly accurate predictions (Baumgartner et al., 2022); b) AI supports decision-making under high uncertainty by using a novel algorithm that weighs alternatives, risks, and cues (Russell & Norvig, 2021); c) AI automates both mundane and highly sophisticated tasks— for example, chatbot customer service applications (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2021); d) Natural Language Processing (NLP) (e.g., digital assistants like Siri or ChatGPT automatic translation and correction tools) enables a computer to analyze, understand, and translate the language of humans so that there is good communication between humans and machines (Chowdhary & Chowdhary, 2020); e) sensory input data can be processed using images, sounds or motions so that the system can identify individual objects, people or situations and respond appropriately (e.g., drones or robots) (Tian et al., 2025).

2. Artificial intelligence in education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has now begun to radically shape the conditions of teaching and learning, influencing pedagogical practice and the way education systems are organized. Though its application is still at an early stage, particularly in public education, the dynamics that are developing are substantial and signify a long-term shift in our

understanding of teaching and the role of the teacher alongside the student-technology relationship (Holmes et al., 2019; Luckin & Holmes, 2016).

AI in education means applying systems able to analyze data, change their actions based on new inputs, and help or assume educational roles. The implementation of such technologies enables among others the personalization of instruction, automatic evaluation, real-time feedback, educational support via digital helpers, smart tutoring systems, and tracking of student advancement. These abilities make AI a key element in improving the learning process particularly in environments with great student variety or limited educational resources (Xie et al., 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

At the international level, since the 2010s, there has been an increase in research in the field of AI in education, with an emphasis on the technological and pedagogical feasibility of its applications (Roll & Wylie, 2016; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). It is important to note that AI is not intended to replace the teacher, but to function as an augmentative tool that can expand their capabilities and enhance learning. The human dimension of teaching, emotional connection with students, managing classroom relationships, and cultivating critical and creative thinking remain areas in which human presence is irreplaceable (Babalís & Tsoli, 2017; Holmes et al., 2019; Selwyn, 2019).

However, the integration of Artificial Intelligence in education is not only accompanied by opportunities, but also by a significant number of challenges and concerns. The main ones are related to issues of privacy, algorithmic bias, transparency and explainability of AI systems' decisions, as well as over-reliance on technologies that may undermine the pedagogical autonomy of the teacher (Holmes et al., 2019; Williamson & Eynon, 2020). At the same time, serious ethical issues are emerging regarding the monitoring of students through learning analytics, the processing of sensitive data, and the use of performance prediction systems, which may reinforce existing inequalities (Schiff, 2022; Selwyn, 2019). For this purpose, there is a need for appropriate training for teachers, both pre-service and in-service, so that they can develop the required knowledge and skills for the critical and pedagogically targeted use of AI in the classroom (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

More than 30 countries have already published national strategies for AI, which define priorities, objectives and frameworks for the application of technology in various social sectors (Schiff, 2022). However, research shows that the connection of AI with education remains limited, with most countries focusing more on how education can support the development of AI, rather than on how AI can transform the educational process itself (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

The use of AI within the educational process (AI for Education – AIED) remains underrepresented in policy strategies. In Schiff's (2022) review of 24 countries, only nine explicitly refer to AI applications in educational practice (e.g., smart tutoring systems and personalized learning tools). At the same time, several jurisdictions have issued substantive education-focused guidance, laying groundwork for future regulation. An OECD review reported that in early 2024 none of the 18 jurisdictions surveyed had enacted binding rules, while nine had already published guidance for generative AI in schools (OECD, 2023). In this direction, the OECD Digital Education Outlook 2023 highlights both the transformative potential of AI in education and the "guidelines and guardrails" needed for effective and equitable implementation (OECD, 2023). Furthermore, in the United Kingdom, the Department for Education has issued guidelines for the safe and responsible use of AI in schools, emphasizing data management and ensuring human pedagogical control (Department for Education, 2023). Spain, in a similar vein, released a Guide on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Education, which aligns with the European Commission's broader AI policy and provides educators with framework material to comprehend AI's implications in the classroom and the necessity of training for safe implementation (Spanish National Institute of Educational Technologies and Teacher Training, 2024).

Moreover, the Council of Europe (2024) is preparing a legally binding instrument for AI in education, emphasizing that regulation must ensure alignment with human rights, democratic values and the rule of law in educational contexts. The European Union, through the AI Act, classifies AI systems used in education as "high risk", introducing

requirements for transparency, data quality control and human oversight (European Data Protection Supervisor, 2025). These priorities align with the Commission's Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027, which focuses on building a high-performance digital education ecosystem and strengthening digital skills and competencies to support education systems' digital transformation (European Commission, 2020).

In Greece, two strategic documents, "A Blueprint for Greece's AI transformation" (2024) and "Generative AI Greece" (2023), set directions for AI in education. The "Blueprint" emphasizes strengthening the system's digital capacity, introducing AI across educational levels, adapting learning environments, providing continuous teacher training and supporting research on pedagogical AI applications (High-Level Advisory Committee on Artificial Intelligence, 2024). "Generative AI Greece" frames generative AI in education as a priority for learning innovation, proposing principles for reliable, transparent and ethical adoption, as well as a testing platform and pilot implementations in schools (EKKE & NCSR "D", 2023). Complementing these, the National Commission on Bioethics and Technoethics (2025) of Greece issued an opinion with legislative proposals and ethical standards for AI in primary and secondary education, while relevant regulatory analysis stresses that AI and algorithmic use must comply with legal, ethical and educational requirements highlighting regulation as a pedagogical-social, not merely technological, issue (Tsaousis & Papastylianos, 2025). The fact that both national governments and international organizations are proceeding with systematic regulation of the use of AI highlights that the challenges are central to the future design of education, underlining the need for careful, ethically informed and pedagogically sensitive integration of technology.

3. Perceptions of pre-service teachers about artificial intelligence as a tool to support their pedagogical work

International research investigating pre-service teachers' perceptions of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has identified several recurring thematic categories that shape how future educators understand, evaluate and envision the pedagogical use of AI. Although these studies come from diverse geographical, cultural and institutional contexts, they could be converged on four central constructs: a. knowledge and conceptual understanding of AI, b. attitudes and perceived pedagogical usefulness, c. digital readiness and self-efficacy, and d. ethical concerns and perceived risks. Structuring the literature according to these categories provides a clearer synthesis and allows for a more systematic comparison with the Greek pre-service teacher context.

A. Knowledge and conceptual understanding of AI

Several studies highlight that pre-service teachers often possess only a surface-level understanding of AI concepts. Pre-service teachers report low levels of factual AI knowledge despite high levels of familiarity with the term "AI" and exposure to AI-powered tools and also remain neutral or negative towards the direct application of AI, indicating a lack of experience and relevant training. Despite their reluctance, more than half of the students express interest in learning about AI and believe that it should be taught in initial teacher education programs (Lucas et al., 2025; Pokrivcakova, 2023). Furthermore, researchers point out that learning experiences with AI (e.g., participating in tele-collaborative lessons using AI) can contribute to the development of more meaningful understanding and improvement in their perception of AI and its potential use in teaching (Uwosomah & Dooly, 2025).

B. Attitudes and perceived pedagogical usefulness

A second cluster of studies focuses on pre-service teachers' attitudes toward the pedagogical value of AI. Pre-service teachers hold positive attitudes perceiving AI as a facilitator of instructional design and assessment (Lozano & Blanco Fontao, 2023; Sanusi et al., 2024; Tejada, 2025), as a supportive tool for personalizing learning (e.g. supporting special educational needs), digital literacy and teaching efficiency (Lamanauskas, 2025) and as a tool with significant

pedagogical potential and a transformative role in learning and teaching (Panagou et al., 2025). Research shows that there are also significant differences in views based on contextual and institutional variations. Access to AI-based platforms had a significant influence on pre-service teachers perceived usefulness of AI (Dumagay et al., 2025), while exposure to Artificial Intelligence during coursework and practicum experiences influenced positively pre-service teachers' attitudes (Ayanwale et al., 2025).

C. Digital readiness and self-efficacy

Digital readiness and self-efficacy strongly shape how confidently pre-service teachers approach AI integration. Although many report solid digital competence, they often feel unprepared to use AI pedagogically (Daher, 2025; Lucas et al., 2025). Higher self-efficacy and perceived ease-of-use predict stronger intentions to adopt AI, whereas AI anxiety can inhibit use, particularly among female students (Zhang et al., 2023). Evidence also suggests that practical skills, more than infrastructure or demographics, drive confidence and readiness (Nancy & Muthupandi, 2025). However, even when students believe they can integrate AI, they may lack key conceptual understanding, ethical awareness, and critical evaluation skills (Guan et al., 2025). This indicates a gap between perceived competence and actual readiness, requiring systematic, targeted training that combines technical preparation with critical and emotional dimensions of AI literacy (Sadaf et al., 2025).

D. Ethical concerns and perceived risks

The fourth thematic cluster concerns pre-service teachers' ethical risks and concerns about AI in education. Across studies, they highlight issues of transparency and privacy (GDPR), the reliability and quality of AI-generated information, and pedagogical risks such as weakened critical thinking, reduced interpersonal communication, and constraints on teacher autonomy (Gamlem et al., 2025; Gatlin, 2023; High-Level Advisory Committee on Artificial Intelligence, 2024; Panagou et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2023). Uwosomah and Dooly (2025) add concerns about student overreliance on generative AI, erosion of creativity, and threats to academic integrity, emphasizing the need for critical digital literacy. Overall, the literature suggests that teacher preparation should combine AI use with critical evaluation so that innovation supports, rather than undermines, the humanistic purposes of education (Uwosomah & Dooly, 2025). The current study is of scientific interest, mainly because it is the first one to explore the knowledge and perceptions on AI from students of the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the NKUA.

4. Methodology and data

Teaching practice is an integral part of initial teacher education in many countries, that links theory to practice through reflective procedures, thus contributing to the formation of teachers as professionals. According to TPACK model (Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge) (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), teachers should possess such knowledge and skills to effectively integrate technology into their teaching process. Its basic principle lies on the idea that successful teaching consists of three interrelated and interconnected dimensions; a) Content Knowledge (CK), i.e. in-depth knowledge of the subject, b) Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), i.e. knowledge of teaching methods, learning process, educational psychology, and c) Technological Knowledge (TK), i.e. knowledge of technological tools and their function. This interaction forms three other dimensions of the model: d) Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), i.e. the way subject knowledge is adapted to teaching practices, e) Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), i.e. the way technology influences or transforms a subject, and f) Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), i.e. the way in which technological tools support and enhance teaching and learning. The combination of the above knowledge and skills composes TPACK, its seventh dimension, which does not function simply as a complementary tool, but rather as an essential means that transforms the learning process into a dynamic and enriched experience.

To this end, the undergraduate study program of the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the NKUA consists of a variety of both compulsory, compulsory elective and elective courses (e.g., Critical Digital Literacy, Educational Robotics with Emerging Learning Technologies) as well as laboratories (e.g., Information and Communication Technologies in Education, Emerging Technologies in Education), that process issues related to the theory and practice of AI, thus completing the triptych, Content, Pedagogical and Technological Knowledge.

Moreover, an integral key and fundamental part of the undergraduate study program is Teaching Practice, which aims, among others, to support pre-service students in applying the philosophy of the TPACK model. More specifically, Teaching Practice at the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the NKUA is implemented in the 2nd, 3rd and 4th year of studies through a series of prerequisite compulsory courses. It is divided into the following three phases: Phase 1 (on-campus skills lab simulation, observation and teaching under the supervision of mentors-school teachers and university coordinators), which takes place within the framework of courses related to Microteaching and General Teaching Methodology (2nd and 3d years of study); Phase 2 (observation and teaching), which takes place within the framework of courses related to teaching concrete subjects in schools in primary education, such as Language, Mathematics and Science (4th year of study); and Phase 3 (familiarization with the school environment and professional identity formation), which consists of independent two-weeks teaching in one class and offers a great opportunity to students to apply the knowledge, skills and attitudes they have gained and developed throughout their studies in real-life school environments (4th year of study). The present study focuses on the knowledge, views and perceptions on AI of pre-service teachers who have completed the 3d Phase of Teaching Practice and seeks to explore the extent to which they apply the Technology dimension of the TPACK model.

The aim of the research is to investigate pre-service teachers': a) knowledge and perceptions of Artificial Intelligence as a tool to support their teaching and b) views on the application of AI in education, based on their experience during the third phase of the teaching practice in primary schools in Athens (Greece). The research questions are as follows:

RQ1. *What is the level of familiarity of pre-service teachers of Primary Education with the concept and basic applications of AI?*

RQ2. *What are the perceptions of pre-service teachers about the potential benefits and challenges of integrating AI into the school context?*

RQ3. *In which pedagogical activities and areas do participants believe that AI can support their work as teachers?*

RQ4. *What kind of AI applications do pre-service teachers use to prepare their teaching within the framework of the University course?*

In RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3, differences observed among participants according to demographic characteristics (gender, age) are also investigated.

Overall, 344 fourth year and graduating students of the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the NKUA participated in the study. Regarding their age, 172 of them (50%) were 22 years old, 48 (14%) were 21 years old, 30 (8.7%) were 23 years old and 94 (27.3%) were 24-48 years old. Moreover, 296 (86%) students were women, 47 (13.6%) students were men, and 1 (0.4%) student did not wish to answer the question.

The research tool used in this study was a structured questionnaire, which was based on the tool developed by Chounta et al. (2022) to investigate the attitudes and perceptions of future teachers towards Artificial Intelligence in education. This tool is an adaptation of the original work of Holder et al. (2018) who had developed a questionnaire to assess the perceptions, attitudes and trust of the public in AI. In the context of this research, the questionnaire was translated and linguistically adapted to Greek, largely maintaining its original structure.

There were ten items in the survey's initial section. However, seven out of ten items were used for the purposes of our study and distributed to the students. The objective of the first two items was to investigate pre-service teachers' individual AI knowledge. The participants were specifically asked to determine their perceived level of AI understanding in the first item. In the second item, participants were given statements regarding artificial intelligence and asked to mark the ones that were true (e.g., AI can perform tasks by replicating human intelligence or AI can modify itself). The third item sought to gauge individuals' level of experience with AI. The purpose of the other two items (4 & 5) was to investigate how pre-service teachers view the application of AI in the classroom. The participants were given lists of AI's advantages (e.g., saving time or making less errors) and disadvantages (e.g., requiring effort to learn how to use it or no trust) and marked the statements that applied for them. A free text component was also provided for participants to submit their input. The final two items (6 & 7) questioned the participants about the aspects of their jobs that might benefit from AI types (e.g., administrative tasks, planning the lesson) and the AI applications they utilized during their Practice for preparing their teaching (e.g., applications for creating quizzes or exercises, assistants for lesson planning or material suggestions, Text-to-speech conversion for students with learning difficulties).

The items in the initial survey that were not used in our study were those that were collecting data regarding the participants' work context and professional role. Furthermore, the open-ended question "If you could have any superpowers you wanted, to help you do your job, what would they be?" that was present in the Chounta et al. (2022) questionnaire was not included in the present study. This decision was made for reasons of adapting the tool to the cultural and linguistic context of the Greek reality, as it was considered that the translation of this specific question – which is based on metaphorical and creative language – may cause ambiguity or misinterpretations among the participants. At the same time, the focus was on collecting answers with more direct application to the assessment of attitudes and knowledge, to maintain the clarity and functionality of the tool in this specific research context.

The research was carried out in the Spring Semester of the academic year 2024-2025. The schools with which the university collaborated for the implementation of the Teaching Practice were 33 in the prefecture of Attica. All participating students were asked to submit mandatory Deliverables within one month of completing their two weeks Teaching Practice. In this context, they were also asked to take part in the research by completing the electronic questionnaire that was uploaded on the eClass platform, a comprehensive e-Course Management System of the NKUA. The duration of completing the questionnaire did not exceed 10 minutes.

In the context of this study, the data analysis was carried out using a combination of quantitative methods with the aim of capturing the perceptions of future teachers regarding Artificial Intelligence. The data were collected via an electronic questionnaire and were processed and investigated based on different statistical tools and techniques. Initially, descriptive statistics were applied to present the basic characteristics of the sample and the general trends in the participants' responses. To investigate possible relationships between variables, correlation analysis was applied with the ϕ (phi) coefficient, which is an equivalent of Pearson for binary (categorical) variables. The correlations between the individual statements concerning positive or negative aspects of AI were illustrated through heatmaps, offering a graphical representation of the proximity between the responses.

At the same time, hierarchical clustering was used to group the responses based on their similarity. The analysis was performed using the Ward method and using the distance index $1 - |\phi|$, as implemented through the `scipy.cluster.hierarchy` library of Python. The results were presented with a dendrogram, which demonstrated distinct groups of attitudes and beliefs in the sample. To examine the independence between categorical variables, such as gender and opinions on individual characteristics of AI, a Chi-square test was applied. The statistical significance level was set at $p < 0.05$, while, where deemed necessary, the Cramér's V coefficient was also calculated, to assess the strength of the correlation between variables.

The statistical analysis was implemented using Python and IBM SPSS software, while the choice of tools aimed at ensuring the reliability and clarity of the findings. Emphasis was placed on the interpretability of the results in the educational context, so that they can support valid pedagogical conclusions.

5. Results

The results from the research on pre-service teachers' address a) level of familiarity with AI (RQ1), b) perceptions about the benefits and challenges of AI in education (RQ2), c) perceptions about the pedagogical activities and areas of their work that AI can support (RQ3) and d) AI applications they use to prepare their teaching (RQ4).

RQ1. What is the level of familiarity of pre-service Primary Education teachers with the concept and basic applications of AI?

The results of the survey on students' knowledge of AI present an interesting distribution. The largest percentage of respondents (71.8%) declare that they know the basics of the concept of AI, which indicates a basic, but not in-depth, familiarity with the subject. In second place, 15.7% of students acknowledge that they have limited knowledge of AI, while 11.9% declare that they know a lot about AI. It is noteworthy that a very small percentage (less than 1%) consider themselves experts in AI, which confirms the need for more specialized training in the field.

The second question examined the participants' basic perceptions regarding the nature of AI. The results indicate that most students correctly identify the basic characteristics of AI. Specifically, the vast majority agreed with the statement that AI can learn from new information and adapt to its environment ($n = 265$), while a large percentage accepted the view that AI does not necessarily have a physical existence, but can exist as software ($n = 232$). In contrast, a very small number of students ($n = 20$) seem to embrace the view that AI can completely replace human intelligence. Most participants also accept the idea that AI is a set of connected entities/machines ($n = 163$) and that it can modify itself ($n = 135$), indicating a general familiarity with its basic operating principles.

In addition, a statistical analysis using a χ^2 test of independence was performed to examine whether there was a correlation between the responses on the nature of AI and the gender of the participants. The resulting p-value was 0.8559, i.e., much greater than the specified significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), indicating that there is no statistically significant differentiation of perceptions based on gender.

Data on the use of AI applications by students reveals a striking trend. 94.8% of respondents state that they have used an AI application, a percentage that demonstrates the extensive penetration of these technologies into the academic and daily lives of young people. This high percentage can be attributed to the increased accessibility of AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Grammarly, translation applications) and their role as aids for study, research, or even entertainment. It is noteworthy that the remaining responses ("Never" and "Don't know") total only 5.2%, which highlights the almost universal adoption of AI in this age group.

RQ2. What are the perceptions of pre-service teachers about the potential benefits and challenges of integrating AI into the school context?

Survey participants highlighted significant positive aspects of AI in their teaching work. The vast majority (281 responses) acknowledged that AI can help save time when searching for materials and content for their course. Also, 199 responses pointed to the potential of AI to help create timetables, while 111 responses said it could reduce errors. However, only 41 responses considered that AI could be useful in marking assignments, which likely reflects the need for human judgment in this area.

Analysis of responses by gender showed similar trends between women and men. For example, 246 women and 34 men chose the option of saving time when searching for material, while 174 women and 24 men highlighted the

creation of timetables. The statistical analysis ($p = 0.244$) confirmed that there are no statistically significant differences in the opinions of the two genders regarding the positive aspects of AI.

Younger participants (under 25 years old) showed a greater preference for the capabilities of AI compared to older age groups. Specifically, 206 responses from participants under 25 mentioned saving time when searching for material, while 145 highlighted the creation of timetables. In contrast, participants over 30 showed relatively less interest in these functions (47 and 29 responses respectively).

To this question, they could identify other positive aspects of AI in their work and gave various answers. Other indicative answers given were: it could give me some ideas for inspiration, so that I can create what I want, it could help me find personalized classroom management methods and creative/experiential/playful activities for lessons aimed at enhancing learning, it could help me easily create interactive ICT and games to enhance the educational process as I do not have personal knowledge of creating software and sites.

Regarding the negative aspects, the survey participants expressed significant concerns about the use of AI in educational practice. The most widespread negative aspect (277 responses) concerns the need for human involvement, with participants arguing that AI cannot meet all the needs of the educational process. This is followed by distrust in the infallible operation of AI (243 responses), as well as the fear that AI could replace human jobs (170 responses). Only a small percentage (18 responses) cited the effort required to learn how to use AI as a problem.

Statistical analysis ($p = 0.0073$) revealed statistically significant differences in opinions by gender. Women expressed a higher level of distrust (216 responses) and strong concern about the need for human involvement (240 responses) compared to men (26 and 36 responses respectively). In addition, women appear to be more cautious about the risk of job loss (147 responses compared to 23 for men).

Younger participants (under 25) showed distrust towards AI, with 168 responses stating that they do not trust its flawless operation and 201 emphasizing the need for human involvement. In contrast, older participants (over 30) showed relatively fewer concerns, with 42 and 40 responses respectively. The 25-30 age group is in an intermediate position. This range of responses may reflect younger people's greater familiarity with the potential and limitations of AI, as well as their sensitivity to issues of trustworthiness and human creativity.

To this question, they could also identify other negative aspects of AI in their work and gave various answers. Some indicative answers given were: It is based on algorithms and data, without pedagogical judgment or emotional intelligence, it limits human creativity, and the value of personal effort is lost, contact with books, research, reflection is lost and critical thinking atrophies, it eliminates personal effort and the effort that needs to be put into a result.

The correlation heatmap (Figure 1), based on the ϕ coefficient (phi), reveals interesting relationships between teachers' positive and negative perceptions of AI. The correlations are displayed in a color-coded manner, with shades of blue representing negative correlations and shades of red representing positive correlations, with the intensity of the color corresponding to the strength of the relationship. It is observed that the correlations are generally weak, with values ranging from -0.17 to +0.24. This suggests that participants do not form clear "camps" for or against AI but rather exhibit a complexity of attitudes that combine both elements. A notable positive correlation (+0.24) is found between the belief that AI can reduce errors and the fear of losing work. On the other hand, negative correlations, such as this one (-0.14) between positive use of AI and distrust of human involvement, indicate that the more educators utilize the potential of AI, the less they tend to perceive it as a threat to the human presence in education. This finding reinforces the idea that practical experience with AI can alleviate some of the initial reservations.

Another statistical analysis that was performed was the dendrogram which depicts the hierarchical clustering of positive and negative aspects of AI and was based on the coefficient $|\phi|$ — the stronger (positive or negative) the correlation, the closer the answers are in the tree (Figure 2). Answers that are closer to the same branch are often selected together and are correlated. The dendrogram was constructed with the help of the linkage function from the Python

scipy library and specifically in the scipy.cluster.hierarchy module which created a $1-|\phi|$ distance matrix, with the vertical axis (values 0.0 to 1.6) showing the "merger height", that is, the distance or difference between the groups that are joined at each point in the tree. The closer $|\phi|$ to 1, the smaller the distance (greater "relatedness") the closer $|\phi|$ to 0, the greater the distance.

Figure 1. Correlation heatmap

We observe that the responses were grouped into 3 clusters, based on how often they are selected together. The first cluster, labeled "Productivity with Concerns," includes teachers who recognize the benefits of AI in saving time and reducing errors, but at the same time express fears about possible loss of work. This group represents dual stance, where acceptance of the practical advantages coexists with concerns about the social implications. The second cluster, labeled "Cautionary Attitude," consists of individuals who use AI selectively, mainly for searching for material, but maintain strong skepticism about its accuracy and its ability to replace human interaction. This group demonstrates a critical attitude towards the potential of AI. The third cluster, labeled "Practical Challenges," describes teachers who mainly face technical difficulties in adopting AI, such as the required learning time. This group focuses on practical barriers to use rather than fundamental reservations.

Figure 2. Hierarchical clustering (dendrogram)

RQ3. In which pedagogical activities and areas do participants imagine that AI can support their work as teachers?

Teachers who participated in the survey showed clear preferences regarding the areas of teaching that they believe can be supported by AI. Lesson planning (223 responses) and lesson content planning (215 responses) emerged as the most popular choices, suggesting that teachers see AI as a useful tool for planning and organizing the teaching process. This is followed by administrative tasks (67 responses), monitoring student learning (49 responses) and assessing their work (42 responses), which highlights a trend towards using AI mainly for thematic and organizational tasks rather than for functions that require deeper pedagogical judgment.

Analysis of responses by gender showed that women more often chose schedule planning (193 responses) and content planning (179 responses) compared to men (29 and 35 responses respectively). However, the statistical test of independence ($X^2= 3.94$, $p = 0.950$) confirmed that there is no statistically significant difference between genders in their preferences.

Younger teachers (under 25 years old) showed particular interest in the use of AI in both schedule planning (163 responses) and content planning (161 responses), while older teachers (over 30 years old) showed relatively less interest (35 and 31 responses respectively). Despite these differences, statistical testing (Chi-Square Test, $X^2 = 3.67$, $p\text{-value} = 0.9612$) showed that age was not a statistically significant factor in participants' preferences. This may be due to the familiarity of all age groups with basic technologies, although younger people tend to utilize them to a greater extent.

To this question, they also specified other activities and areas that AI can support their work such as: Through smart applications and systems, it can enhance student participation with games, quizzes, virtual assistants or simulations, it could be used to modify educational material so that it becomes understandable for children with developmental disorders and/or special educational needs, it is quite useful in terms of searching for additional material for a lesson, perhaps it could archive student performance so that I don't have to look through many old documents.

RQ4. What kind of AI applications do they use to prepare their teaching within the framework of the University course?

The analysis shows that the most popular category of AI tools used by teachers are assistants for lesson planning or material suggestions (e.g., ChatGPT, Curipod), with 230 participants reporting their use. This is followed by applications for creating quizzes or exercises, with 199 users. The lowest use is observed in tools for personalizing learning (49 people) and in text-to-speech applications (57 people), which may address more specialized needs. Also, the relatively low use of automated correction tools (24 users) may be due to the existence of established assessment methods. The existence of 30 entries as 'Other' suggests that a portion of teachers may also use alternative or less common tools, which were not included in the proposed options.

The study of the correlation between the answers to this question and the answers to the question "Which areas of your teaching could be supported by Artificial Intelligence (multiple choice)" using the Cramer's V coefficient, yielded very low values, indicating limited or zero statistical correlation between the area of teaching and the specific tools. To answer this question, they also gave various answers apart from the ones in the questionnaire. Indicatively: Image creation applications (e.g., Canvas), I don't use any now, Canva, Elevenlabs, Tokkingheads, animateddrawings.

6. Discussion and conclusions

This research shed light on the familiarity, perceptions and AI applications of pre-service teachers that completed their studies at the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the NKUA in the academic year 2024-2025. More specifically, it seems that many students are familiar with the concept and basic applications of AI. At the same time, a significant group remains distant from the subject, either due to lack of information, low digital-confidence or limited educational exposure, as indicated in other research findings as well (Gatlin, 2023; Guan et al., 2025; Lucas et al., 2025; Unal, 2025). The participants' perceptions regarding the nature of AI are comparable regardless of their gender.

Moreover, a high percentage of the students have used an AI application, a percentage that far exceeds those in other European studies (Lamanauskas, 2025; Lucas et al., 2025), where the use of AI was limited or occasional. This difference can be attributed both to the growing popularity of tools such as ChatGPT, and to the ease of access they offer to students who are asked to design lessons, create activities or search for educational materials. Despite the extensive use, the present study shows that this use is mainly limited to auxiliary teaching design tools and is not accompanied by a deep understanding of the pedagogical or ethical aspects of technology, a fact that is also confirmed by the relevant literature (Chounta et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023).

According to the present study, future teachers recognize the advantages of AI tools in their work, mostly concentrating on saving time when searching for materials and content for their course, afterwards on creating timetables and finally on marking assignments, positive aspects that have also been reported in other studies as well (Lozano & Blanco Fontao, 2023). This finding highlights the importance of AI as a tool for optimizing lesson preparation. In fact, the use of AI in education is not influenced by gender but is a common need for all teachers. A difference was detected between younger and older participants, with the first group showing greater preference in the capabilities of AI, probably due to the greater familiarity of younger people with new technologies and their flexibility in adopting innovative tools.

At the same time, participants share the same concerns regarding the disadvantages of AI, with women and younger participants being more skeptical on issues, such as job loss, distrust and need for human involvement, negative aspects which have been identified in several studies (Gatlin, 2023; Haseski, 2019). These differences may be due to social or cultural factors that influence women's perception of technological change (Zhang et al., 2023). Plus, it seems that educators who recognize the practical benefits of AI tend to also express concerns about its socioeconomic implications. This ambivalence has been recorded in other studies, such as Lamanauskas (2025) and Alwaqdani (2024), where participants recognized both benefits and risks. This degree of distrust observed in our research is likely due to the rapid development of AI in recent years and the ethical doubts raised by systems such as chatbots (Govers et al., 2025; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

Furthermore, most participants believe that AI can support them in lesson planning and lesson content planning. This perception is consistent with the findings of Fošner (2024), according to which undergraduate students tend to view AI as a technological aid, rather than an active pedagogical agent. The absence of deeper engagement with advanced applications of AI (e.g., personalized teaching, predictive assessment, support for students with disabilities and/or special educational needs) could be attributed to several factors, such as lack of AI-related resources (Li & Zhang, 2020), lack of familiarity with the resources (Hur, 2024), perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and social influences (Wang & Li, 2019), mismatches between beliefs that AI is useful and reality, knowledge on how to integrate it effectively to reach the learning goals (Guan et al., 2025) and indicates the need for its systematic integration into the curriculum.

Cluster analysis and φ correlations revealed three distinct groups of attitudes: a group that sees AI as a tool for improvement with parallel concern (dual stance), a second that maintains a cautious and selective use, and a third that identifies practical obstacles (such as learning difficulties or lack of training). This polyphony clearly reflects that the attitudes of future teachers are not unidimensional but consist of a spectrum from functional acceptance to pedagogical reservation, which is also confirmed by studies (Chounta et al., 2022; Holmes et al., 2019). These are disparities that need to be addressed through effective training programs to develop self-efficacy in AI usage in teaching, learning and assessment (Gamlem et al., 2025) and practice on combining the Content, Pedagogical and Technological Knowledge (Nicolay et al., 2021; Peura et al., 2021). Despite quantitative differences, attitudes towards the use of AI are not influenced by gender but are a common trend among all teachers. Age was not a statistically significant factor in participants' preferences. The statistically insignificant differences by gender and age are consistent with Prasetya et al.'s (2024) study,

highlighting that these factors are not critical determinants of attitude. However, the high acceptance of AI by younger teachers reinforces Kim's (2025) view of generational differences in technological fluency. Finally, the most common AI applications used by the students for preparing their course were assistants for lesson planning or material suggestions, while the less preferable use was tools for personalizing learning and in text-to-speech applications, perhaps revealing insufficient knowledge leading to superficial application, emphasis on basic digital literacy, unaware of the benefits on specific student groups, difficulty in connecting the technological with the pedagogical content, etc.

Future teachers acknowledge AI's potential and use it to a limited extent, but they need structured training and critical guidance to apply it pedagogically rather than technocratically. This requires understanding how AI supports learning, along with research/data-literacy and management/teamwork skills (Luckin & Holmes, 2016). In Greece, adoption is generally favored within a human-pedagogical frame, yet systematic preparation and empirical classroom application remain limited.

This study has some limitations. The data was collected from only one Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education and not all of them. Moreover, the number of participants is small; this means that the results cannot be generalized beyond that group. The data was selected relying on self-reported items, which can introduce bias. Finally, there is a limited scope regarding the participants' demographics. Gender and age are included in this study, while other information (e.g., nationality and socioeconomic level) was not included in the objectives of this study. Based on the results of the research, some suggestions that could be introduced are: Students studying the teaching profession should learn about AI tools and applications in the context of both teacher initial and subsequently continuing training; Teaching Practice in Universities should also focus on AI applications; Future teachers should have the opportunities to get acquainted and apply a wide spectrum of AI tools for meeting many educational needs, such as preparing the lesson, evaluating the students, supporting students with learning difficulties, disabilities and/or special educational needs; Further research over time to monitor the evolution of perceptions and to deepen on the causes of these perceptions.

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